

Some Solutions to Help Students Enjoy Learning English More

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Abstract:

When teaching a large class of students, the teacher's biggest concern is which method to use to partially satisfy the learning needs of the majority of students. Each class has its unique characteristics, different learning needs, and the same level of students between classes at Tan Trao University. Some methods work well for one class, but not for another. This concern becomes much greater when the level of the student and the level of the curriculum has quite a big difference. Teachers often have to add the function of "curriculum designer" for a particular class. In addition to teaching according to the school's general curriculum, teachers must prepare more types of exercises and support activities to help students

become more interested in learning and learn English more effectively. In this research paper, the writer of this article would like to mention some solutions that I have applied to students of Kindergarten Class C K8 and their feedback on my solution.

Keywords: *Enjoy learning english, curriculum designer, support activities, Tan Trao University, teaching.*

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Introduction

"Talking to a person in their language is touching their heart." - Nelson Mandela.

Every human being in the modern world needs to know at least one foreign language. Knowing a foreign language is not only an indispensable requirement of highly technical workers to meet the constantly renewed technological processes, but knowing and being fluent in foreign languages is also an indispensable skill in the booming era. information technology explosion and the current context of economic integration and rapid economic growth in Vietnam.

In recent years, along with the trend of globalization and international integration,

Vietnam has been strengthening exchanges and expanding cooperation relations with countries around the world in all aspects. International exchange and cooperation require communication and information exchange between countries, but the language barrier is one of the top difficulties, posing an important problem that requires foreign language proficiency, for each Vietnamese citizen. In Decision 1400/QĐ-TTĐ dated September 30, 2008, the Prime Minister emphasized the goal that "by 2020, the majority of young Vietnamese who graduate from high schools, colleges and universities will have sufficient foreign language skills. use independently, confidently in communication, learning, and working in an

integrated multilingual, multicultural environment...»). For students, learning a foreign language really not only allows for more job search opportunities, but also helps them to add more knowledge of human culture, making an important contribution to the needs of society. integration and cooperation between our country and the world. The Minister of Education and Training has issued a Directive on 9 main tasks for the 2016-2017 school year, including the task of «Improving the quality of foreign language teaching at all levels and training levels».

Vietnam's opening up, integration, and market economy integration requires a huge human resource with foreign language skills. Moreover, the high demand for entertainment and travel also creates a society, a community that invests regularly in learning foreign languages. However, current foreign language learning for different subjects has different methods depending on the conditions of each subject, mainstream learning and non-formal learning, face-to-face learning or distance learning, offline learning, and learning online. In addition to studying a foreign language in the main course, there are also classroom activities, extra-classroom activities, and extra-curricular activities using foreign languages that are increasingly popular and highly effective, encouraging students to learn foreign languages.

Results and Discussion

In order for students to be "interested in learning foreign languages", first of all, it is necessary to build a favorable environment to support foreign language teaching and learning and create motivation and interest in foreign language learning for students. Detail:

Determine the right foreign language learning goals for each subject. For students of universities and colleges specializing in foreign languages, foreign languages play a key role. But for students of universities and colleges who do not specialize in foreign languages, foreign languages only play an auxiliary role, using foreign languages in future work, or for personal purposes (traveling, casual

communication with foreigners...). For example, a web developer will only need foreign languages when communicating with foreign customers; an import-export employee will only need foreign languages to do import-export documents... And also on this principle, teachers determine how to teach students to achieve their goals, learners will be interested, and the work-study with high results.

Creating a foreign language learning community - the association of a group of learners, having the same needs, a desire, and learning interests, with the forms, ways, and methods of learning actively selected, together to build a voluntary «playground» (Clear, N/A). The members of the learning community have a need and feel attached to this community environment, to learn together, share, help each other, and build, maintain and develop the community. The learning environment is a self-organizing learning environment with highly diverse, interactive, and flexible characteristics.

Connect to the community system. In their activities, in addition to successfully connecting individual students, lecturers, and groups working together within the framework of a school, it is necessary to pay attention to having activities to connect schools with universities. each other, or between smaller groups working (Long, 2016) with the same purpose and method, to create a wider network of connections, learning and sharing experiences with each other, and developing into a network of connections. large community among schools within and outside the region. This connection is being actively implemented by the Pushkin Institute.

Innovating the way of teaching and learning foreign languages. Resolution 29/NQ/TW dated November 4, 2013, of the 8th Conference of the 11th Central Executive Committee on a fundamental and comprehensive renovation of education and training, stated: "Fundamental and comprehensive innovation in education and training is the renewal of major, core and urgent issues, from viewpoints and guiding ideas to objectives, contents, methods, mechanisms, and policies. , conditions to ensure implementation

and renewal from the leadership of the Party, the management of the State to the governance of education and training institutions, and the participation of the family, community, society, and learners themselves. Innovation at all levels and disciplines».

Socializing resources to support teaching and learning foreign languages increases learners' interest. Contributions of organizations and individuals outside the society will make up for the meager budget funding for these activities. The mobilization of external resources (human and material) into the activities to support teaching and learning foreign languages will enrich the activities and develop the scale. For example, for the organization of foreign language competitions, festivals, and large-scale exchanges (from 100 to 500 students), it is necessary to have sponsorship from units, individuals, or contributions part of the attendees.

There are many specific measures to make learners love foreign language subjects more, and encourage students to actively study foreign languages.

Innovating the way of teaching foreign languages and the form of testing and assessment.

Innovating examination and assessment towards focusing on assessing the quality and capacity of students. Focus on process assessment: classroom assessment; evaluated by comments; strengthening the form of assessment through group exercises; Presentations; combining the results of the assessment during the learning process and the summative assessment at the end of the semester and at the end of the school year. All forms of examination and assessment are aimed at developing students' capacity; encouraging students' efforts and interest in learning; Encourage learners to apply what they have learned. Actively combine in a reasonable and appropriate manner the form of essay test with the objective test, between theory test and practice test in foreign language tests; implementing the essay test in the written tests of foreign languages; assigning exercises that require more group interaction as well as helping

students to actively create and practice better language skills.

Focus on teaching listening and speaking, developing listening and speaking skills, and communicating in foreign languages.

Encourage students to speak, and communicate, and create opportunities for students to communicate simply in foreign language lessons.

Greg and Angela Thomson said, “The only way you can speak a new language is to start speaking it, no matter how poorly!” The most appreciated and shared view of teaching and learning a foreign language today is the action and demand point of view. Learners are not merely passive recipients of knowledge, but actively, learners actually become language users to interact with others. Teachers can encourage children to talk, start class by using simple questions, ask students what they did last week/weekend or the night before so that they can talk about themselves naturally; ask students for information they know well, or ask them about places to visit; for students to participate in activities during class, on the board (such as asking to spell out a word the teacher is writing, or complete a sentence, write a question or correct a mistake on the board, etc.) Games and simple crosswords with hints are also good ways.

It is necessary to further strengthen the application of information technology in teaching and learning foreign languages, and improve students' learning efficiency through the application of new information technology achievements. The application of information technology by teachers to the teaching process (design or use of websites, online foreign language teaching programs, or teaching software) to improve students' autonomy and learning motivation; and especially expand the ability to interact with subject content, with teachers, with learners' classmates, stimulate learners' interest, as well as their responsibility for the language learning process (Murray & Greenberg, 2000).

Students can be encouraged to take online courses, as learners can easily access the course

through the Internet and other forms of digital technology.

Websites and online foreign language teaching materials can be used to organize various types of activities to support foreign language teaching and learning.

Applying a direct interactive online learning model.

This is a new learning model, which will be applied for the first time by the Pushkin Institute in Vietnam in teaching and learning Russian. This learning model has inherited all the advantages of both Online and Offline learning models. This model is deployed in each class with topics corresponding to each learner's level. Learners will be able to study directly on the spot with native experts, the program is suitable for their level, the best support in learning, immediate difficult questions and answers, and organized learning (Eliason, 2017). Systematic and scientific practice, bringing the best learning effect to learners. This learning model certainly brings a lot of excitement to students, because of the direct interaction, and because of its practicality and convenience.

Create the most favorable conditions for the variety of scientific materials, helping students have the best learning environment, easy, convenient, and complete search for learning materials in the learning process, with a technology platform that allows continuous exchange and sharing of learning experiences to effective and successful learning. Teachers need to focus on providing required resources and additional reading for students to refer to. The library or library of the school must also be a place to provide all necessary documents and study space so that students can exploit that resource optimally.

Another information channel is an online resource that is accessed via the Internet. Students can exploit information anywhere as long as they connect to the Internet, and have many favorable conditions to access diverse and especially up-to-date digital resources.

Organize various types of activities to support foreign language teaching and learning.

Organizing extracurricular activities for students, language clubs, cultural programs using foreign languages, and competitions in foreign languages. Currently, many new ideas, and new ways of doing things for units and colleges - universities are being implemented, attracting the attention and enthusiastic participation of a large number of students and teachers, creating a positive effect. very active for the goal of learning foreign languages with quality and efficiency. These are the models and programs:

- Foreign Language Club.
- Student exchange programs in some countries such as the Philippines, Thailand, Laos, USA, UK...
- Karaoke in foreign languages
- English Olympics.
- Essay writing contest, presentation, poetry reading in the foreign language
- Composing and performing art contests in foreign languages
- Culture Festival
- Foreign language forums, Galas, evenings (using foreign languages) of colleges and universities
- Summer camp, English cultural exchange
- Sightseeing, picnic with the theme "Let's speak English"
- Outdoor language classes, in the cafe.

Use volunteers and native speakers.

This is a force that needs to be utilized to participate in foreign language teaching and exchange and extracurricular activities with students. Learners are always interested in interacting, communicating, communicating, and learning with native speakers. Because learning a foreign language is not just learning a language, but also learning the culture, customs,

and way of life of the people who use that language.

Should encourage making friends, and learning foreign languages with native speakers in person or online. Teaching and learning foreign languages not only uses face-to-face - offline methods but also needs to develop more online activities at the same time, such as e-club models, e-games, and Facebook groups.

In a dynamic and increasingly globalized world, each person must locate himself, and one of the ways is to learn a foreign language - the common language of the world. To encourage students to love and learn foreign languages, first of all, it is necessary to create interest in learning foreign languages for learners. In short, teachers need to guide students on how to effectively use and practice what they have learned; apply forms of reward to encourage, motivate and encourage learners to love foreign languages more.

We think, there will be a lot of new ideas from colleagues. Hope to hear and reach out.

Conclusion

Finally, the choice of teaching method can be based on the teacher's own experience but must pay attention to the student's interest in the lesson as well as their ability. Depending on the pedagogical capacity and aptitude of each lecturer, the selection of methods is effective. Teachers need to know the qualifications and competence of the subjects they are about to teach, from there, they can propose appropriate activities. Choosing teaching methods is an important factor for subjects in general and English in particular. The selection of appropriate methods involves many factors, requiring lecturers to have certain qualifications

and pedagogical capacity, to be attentive to listen, observe, understand students, to combine with other elements of available means and techniques, from which teaching can be highly effective.

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